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Abstract

African literature often employs linguistic and culture-bound stylistic elements within colonial languages, such as French and English. This poses certain difficulties in translation. In the current study, attention is drawn to the authorial style as a central part of African literary texts. Existing studies on Francophone African prose have predominantly focused on just literary and linguistic concerns, with little attention paid to exploring stylistic figures through translation. I aim to conduct a stylistic investigation of selected Francophone African novels and their English translations, to identify and explore cultural and linguistic challenges encountered by the translators. The study draws excerpts chosen from the translations of Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë* and Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre* and their source texts to examine the original authors' stylistic choices. The research employs Gideon Toury's *Descriptive Translation Studies* and the *Manipulation Theory* of Susan Bassnett and André Lefevere as the theoretical frameworks. The data will be subjected to qualitative analysis, and these analyses will demonstrate the challenges and the effects of the translator's choices in domesticating or foreignizing Francophone African writers' styles, such as the use of culture-bound terms, repetition patterns, musical/rhythmic effects, gender-specific/gender-neutral language, and punctuation. This study proposes strategies for more effective cultural mediation of aesthetics in Francophone African novels. Ultimately, the work seeks to enhance the appreciation of the Francophone African prose and contribute to the cross-cultural discourse of stylistic translation.

Keywords: Domestication, Foreignization, Style, Translation, Francophone African Prose